

Horizon 2020
Programme

D 2.4: Acceptance Report

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1. Executive summary

This deliverable reports on the stakeholders' acceptance of the proposed Sm@RT solutions. It presents two types of data:

- 1) Data gathered from the evaluation of PLF and DT innovative technology solutions (identified in D2.2) by stakeholders involved in the small ruminant meat and dairy industries across Europe and Israel during the Training sessions and Demo Days.
- 2) Results from a series of workshops sessions using the Adoption and Diffusions Outcome Prediction Tool (ADOPT) (<https://adopt.csiro.au/home.aspx>), which allow participants to assess factors influencing the rate and peak level of uptake of the tools and technologies selected as solutions (from D2.2).

This 2-prongs approach allowed to understand and appreciate stakeholders' acceptance of the innovative solutions proposed by the Sm@RT project.

2. Methodology

2.1. Evaluation of the solutions during training and farm demonstration sessions on Digifarms and Innovative Farms.

The results contain the evaluation of the PLF and innovative DT solutions that were selected by the countries (Task 2.2) and that answer the needs of farmers (D2.1.).

In each country, in combination with the cost-benefit analysis performed in Task 3.2, (D3.2) farmers and practitioners were invited to evaluate the technologies through 2 mechanisms:

- 1) a series of training and practical days on the Digifarms, research centres equipped with technologies where they were able to use and handle the technologies shown by researchers and
- 2) a series of visits to Innovative Farms (IF), private commercial farms to foster exchanges with the small ruminant industry, at key animal or data handling times according to the production types, where they had a practical experience of using the different technologies, shown by farmers for farmers. Both approaches were complementary each other.

All sessions were organized in order to provide tangible knowhow on practice and to allow the farmers to see, experience and understand in practice how the different technologies work on farms.

In some cases, the training sessions were carried out on Innovative Farms, but with the addition of some interventions and presentations by Digifarms' research staff (hybrid approach).

The total number of sessions organised and the tools evaluated are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Sessions and tools evaluated, by country

Country	Estonia	France	Hungary	Ireland	Italy	Israel	Norway	UK
Number of sessions	3	4	1	3	4	2	1	3
Tools evaluated	Post-dry hay technology Milking parlour (EID eartags & readers) Milking parlour (automatic concentrate feeder) Milk feeder for kids EID stick reader EID weigh crate	Walk Over Weigh Weighing and sorting gate Water meter + EID Virtual fences Milk tank weighing Drone Camera Automatic feeder Straw blower Heat detector (Alpha detector) Happy grass GPS collars Baoba app	Automatic milk feeder EID stick reader EID weigh crate Mixer & feeder wagon Pregnancy scanner Tru-Test weigh head	Weighing and sorting gate Smartfence EID wand EID handheld Data recording apps Conveyor Weather station Pasturebase Ireland Cameras EID weigh crate	Walk Over Weigh Weighing and sorting gate Milk tank weighing Individual milk meter Environmental station EID reader Automatic feeder Portable SCC Portable NIRS Concentrate dispenser Electric brushes Feeding software Photovoltaic	Weighing device GPS for grazing Smart individual collar EID reader Management software Weighing trough	Virtual fences Drone EID stick reader Sheep recording system (management software)	Tru-Test & weigh head EID Stick reader Psion Combi-clamp + weigh head DNA parentage EID auto-drafter Farm management software Portable Accumulation Chambers (for methane emissions) & automatic feeders

2.1.1. Digifarms sessions

Digifarms visits/training sessions: on each Digifarm, 1- 2 training sessions have been organised for ~ 8-10 farmers each time. During these sessions, the farmers were able to use the technologies in a real-life situation, learn how to use them with animals, how to upload or download the collected information, etc.

The 3rd series of National Workshops were designed to evaluate the innovative PLF and DT solutions in each country Digifarm and was done in parallel with the training session. Some countries also carried out training sessions during the 4th series of National Workshops.

Participants attending these events were asked a series of questions on each tool covered during the training sessions. After using/observing each tool, the participants were asked to fill in an individual questionnaire, to gauge whether or not they changed their views and opinions of the tool.

Individual questionnaire

Name of PLF tool tested :				
<i>Please tick your answer</i>	1 (Not at all)	2 (No)	3 (Yes)	4 (Yes a lot)
1. Did you have the tool on your farm?				
2. Did you like it?				
2. Was it easy to use?				
3. Would you have the infrastructure needed to implement it?				
4. Could you implement it on your farm easily?				
5. Is it affordable to you?				
6. Could you justify investing in it?				
7. Do you think it would take long to pay it back?				
8. Do you understand better after training?				
9. Would you recommend to somebody else?				
10. Do you think you need more training/guides/YouTube video to use it more often?				

Moreover, before and after the training, the participants were asked to answer the following questions for each technology tested.

Name of PLF tested			
<i>Please tick your answer</i>	<i>Maybe</i>	<i>No</i>	<i>Yes</i>
<i>BEFORE - what do you think of this technology?</i>			
<i>BEFORE - would you put it on your farm?</i>			
<i>AFTER - what do you think of this technology?</i>			
<i>AFTER - would you put it on your farm?</i>			

2.1.2. Innovative farm sessions

A number of farm demonstration events on the innovative farms in each country have also been held, to collate information on farmers' views of the PLF and DT solutions. On each innovative farm, one demonstration or shadowing session were organised for 2-6 farmers (M2.3). These sessions were focused on how the innovative farmer is using a particular technology, and allowed the other farmers to ask practical questions, use the technology if possible, and discuss any issues. These sessions were focused on information from farmers to farmers, in a smaller committee and in a more practical situation than the Digifarms sessions.

Participants attending these events were asked a series of questions on each tool covered during the day to record the impact of the training/demonstration.

Before/After questionnaires on Innovative farms

Name of PLF tool tested :			
<i>Please tick your answer</i>	<i>1 (Not)</i>	<i>2 (Not sure)</i>	<i>3 (Yes)</i>
<i>BEFORE - Do you have this tool ?</i>			
<i>BEFORE - Do you think it is worth investing in it?</i>			
<i>BEFORE - Would you like to implement it on your farm?</i>			
<i>BEFORE - Level of practicality (1=low; 4=high)</i>			
<i>AFTER - Do you think it is worth investing in it?</i>			
<i>AFTER - Would you like to implement it on your farm?</i>			
<i>AFTER - Level of practicality (1=low; 4=high)</i>			

2.2. The ADOPT tool

To assess factors influencing the rate and peak level of uptake of the tools and technologies selected as solutions (presented previously in D2.2), stakeholder groups in the 8 Sm@RT countries (Estonia, France, Hungary, Ireland, Israel, Italy, Norway, UK) used the Adoption and Diffusions Outcome Prediction Tool (ADOPT) (<https://adopt.csiro.au/home.aspx>). During the international visit to New Zealand earlier in the project (presented previously in D1.3), the project team were introduced to the ADOPT programme by researchers at AgResearch. In addition to the evaluations mentioned above, the project team decided that using the ADOPT programme would provide additional information in terms of the future acceptance of the proposed solutions.

2.2.1. The ADOPT process

Detailed background for the ADOPT programme is provided by Kuehne *et al.* (2017) and summarised on the CSIRO (Commonwealth Scientific and Industrial Research Organisation) associated ADOPT website (<https://adopt.csiro.au/home.aspx>). The 22 questions asked were structured around 4 aspects of adoption; characteristics of the tool/technology; characteristics of the farming population; advantage of using the tool/technology; and learnability. The responses given to each question allow a number of factors to be calculated, allowing the peak adoption level and the time to near-peak adoption to be predicted. The time to near-peak adoption level is the time it takes to reach 99% of the predicted peak level of adoption.

Details of the 22 questions asked are given in Table 2.

Table 2. Overview of the questions asked during each ADOPT (Adoption and Diffusions Outcome Prediction Tool) session

Category	ADOPT variable	Question asked
Relative advantage for the population	1. Profit orientation	What proportion of the target population has maximising profit as a strong motivation?
	2. Environmental orientation	What proportion of the target population has protecting the natural environment as a strong motivation?
	3. Risk orientation	What proportion of the target population has risk minimization as a strong motivation?
	4. Enterprise scale	On what proportion of the target farms is there a major enterprise that could benefit from the innovation?
	5. Management horizon	What proportion of the target population has long-term (greater than 10 years) management horizon for their farm?
	6. Short-term constraints	What proportion of the target population is under conditions of severe short-term financial constraints?
Learnability characteristics of the innovation	7. Trialling ease	How easily can the practice (or significant components of it) be trialled on a limited basis before a decision is made to adopt it on a larger scale?

	8. Practice complexity	Does the complexity of the innovation allow the effects of its use to be easily evaluated when it is used?
	9. Observability	To what extent would the innovation be observable to farmers who are yet to adopt it when it is used in their district?
Population-specific influence on the ability to learn about the innovation	10. Advisory support	What proportion of the target population uses paid advisors capable of providing advice relevant to the innovation?
	11. Group involvement	What proportion of the target population participates in farmer-based groups that discuss farming?
	12. Relevant existing skills & knowledge	What proportion of the target population will need to develop substantial new skills and knowledge to use the innovation?
	13. Practice awareness	What proportion of the target population would be aware of the use of trialling of the innovation in their district?
Relative advantage of the innovation	14. Relative upfront cost of the practice	What is the size of the up-front cost of the investment relative to the potential annual benefit from using the innovation?
	15. Reversibility of the practice	To what extent is the adoption of the innovation able to be reversed?
	16. Profit benefit in years that it is used	To what extent is the use of the innovation likely to affect the profitability of the farm business in the years that it is used?
	17. Profit benefit in future	To what extent is the use of the innovation likely to have additional effects on the future profitability of the farm business?
	18. Time for profit benefit to be realized	How long after the innovation is first adopted would it take for the effects on future profitability to be realized?
	19. Environmental impact	To what extent would the use of the innovation have net environmental benefits or costs?
	20. Time for environmental impacts to be realized	How long after the innovation is first adopted would it take for the expected environmental benefits or costs to be realized?
	21. Risk	To what extent would the use of the innovation affect the net exposure of the farm business to risk?
	22. Ease and convenience	To what extent would the use of the innovation affect the ease and convenience of the management of the farm in the years that it is used?

For each question, a selection of possible answers was provided to the participants. Where individual participants chose several different answers, the answer with the majority of votes was then used as the final answer going forward in the analyses.

The conceptual framework used by the ADOPT process is shown in Figure 1. Kuehne et al. (2017) identified two overarching factors that were influential in the adoption process: the relative advantage of the practice/innovation and the effectiveness of the process of learning about practice/innovation. The relative advantage is regarded as the main driver of how many in a population decide to adopt, whereas the learning process will influence the time interval before decisions are made to adopt the practice/innovation. Additionally, these can be split into two further categories, relating to characteristics of the target population and of the practice/innovation. This therefore provides four sets of issues to be considered, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1 The basic conceptual framework shows relationships between: learning, relative advantage, the population and the practice. (Adapted from Kuehne et al. 2017)

The two learning quadrants on the left-hand side of Figure 1 influence the time taken to reach near-peak adoption. The right-hand side of Figure 1 associated with the advantage, influence the peak level of adoption.

2.2.2. Data collection sessions

Most of the ADOPT sessions to date have been carried out by each project partner during, or shortly after, recent National and Transnational workshops (NWS4, NWS5 & TNWS4, TNWS5). During each session, participants were shown details about the tool or technology that they were going to be focussing on. Some of these were in person (i.e. after a training or demonstration session) or online using the solution information prepared previously. A record was kept of the roles each participant in the group had, for example farmer, researcher or an advisor. Each participant was encouraged to select an answer, from the selection provided, for each question. If a range of different answers were received, the most popular answer would be selected and used for the analyses.

Details of the different ADOPT sessions carried out so far in each partner country (additional sessions are planned during the remainder of the project) are given in Tables 3 to 10.

Table 3 Details on the tools/technologies assessed by participants in Estonia

Country	Tool/Technology	Event	Total number of participants	Number of Farmers	Number of Researchers	Number of Advisors	Other
Estonia	EID stick reader	NWS4	3	2		1	
	EID weigh crate	NWS4	7	4		1	2
	Drone	TNWS4	7	5	2		
	Virtual Fence	TNWS4	7	5	2		
	Water meter	TNWS5					

NWS4 – National Workshop 4; TNWS4 Trans-national Workshop 4; TNWS5 – Trans-national Workshop 5

Table 4 Details on the tools/technologies assessed by participants in France

Country	Tool/Technology	Event	Total number of participants	Number of Farmers	Number of Researchers	Number of Advisors	Other
France	Walk over weigher (dairy goat)	NWS4	10	4	3	2	1
	Walk over weigher (dairy sheep)	NWS4	7	4	2	1	
	Walk over weigher (meat sheep)	NWS4	7	3	2	1	1
	Automatic feeder	TNWS5	9	1	6		2

NWS4 – National Workshop 4; TNWS4 Trans-national Workshop 4; TNWS5 – Trans-national Workshop 5

Table 5 Details on the tools/technologies assessed by participants in Hungary

Country	Tool/Technology	Event	Total number of participants	Number of Farmers	Number of Researchers	Number of Advisors	Other
Hungary	EID stick reader	NWS4	10	7	1	2	
	Camera	TNWS4	6	3	1	1	1
	RFID database	TNWS4	6	3	1	1	1
	Pregnancy scanning	TNWS5	8	4	2	1	1

NWS4 – National Workshop 4; TNWS4 Trans-national Workshop 4; TNWS5 – Trans-national Workshop 5

Table 6 Details on the tools/technologies assessed by participants in Ireland

Country	Tool/Technology	Event	Total number of participants	Number of Farmers	Number of Researchers	Number of Advisors	Other
Ireland	EID stick reader	NWS4	12	3	4	2	3
	Drone	TNWS4	5	3	2		
	RFID database	TNWS4	5	3	2		
	Camera	TNWS4	5	3	2		
	Connected Fence	TNWS5	4	1	2		1

NWS4 – National Workshop 4; TNWS4 Trans-national Workshop 4; TNWS5 – Trans-national Workshop 5

Table 7 Details on the tools/technologies assessed by participants in Israel

Country	Tool/Technology	Event	Total number of participants	Number of Farmers	Number of Researchers	Number of Advisors	Other
Israel	Water trough (1)	NWS4	8	4	2	2	
	Water trough (2)	Industry meeting				7	
	GPS collars	TNWS4	10	6	2	2	
	Milk feeder	TNWS5	12	4	4	4	

NWS4 – National Workshop 4; TNWS4 Trans-national Workshop 4; TNWS5 – Trans-national Workshop 5

Table 8 Details on the tools/technologies assessed by participants in Italy

Country	Tool/Technology	Event	Total number of participants	Number of Farmers	Number of Researchers	Number of Advisors	Other
Italy	EID (bolus) parlour reader (dairy sheep)	NWS4	19	7	6		6
	EID (bolus) parlour reader (dairy goat)	NWS4	20	8	9		3
	Milkimeters (dairy goat)	NWS4	20	8	9		3
	Milkimeters (dairy sheep)	NWS4	19	7	6		6
	Autodrafter (dairy goat)	NWS4	20	8	9		3

	Autodrafter (dairy sheep)	NWS4	19	7	6		6
	Milk tank weighing	TNWS5	10	2	7		1
	Camera (dairy goats)	TNWS4	8	8			
	GPS (dairy sheep)	TNWS4	8	8			

NWS4 – National Workshop 4; TNWS4 Trans-national Workshop 4; TNWS5 – Trans-national Workshop 5

Table 9 Details on the tools/technologies assessed by participants in Norway

Country	Tool/Technology	Event	Total number of participants	Number of Farmers	Number of Researchers	Number of Advisors	Other
Norway	Virtual Fence	NWS4	8	7		1	
	GPS Sheep	T/NWS4	9	9			
	RFID database	T/NWS4	9	9			
	Drone	T/NWS4	5	5			
	Fire detection system	T/NWS4	9	9			
	Virtual Fence	T/NWS4	10	10			
	Camera	T/NWS4	8	8			
	GPS Sheep	STG meeting	6	3	2	1	
	Conveyor	TNWS5	10	6	4		

NWS4 – National Workshop 4; T/NWS4 – Combined Trans-national and National Workshop 4; TNWS5 – Trans-national Workshop 5

Table 10- Details on the tools/technologies assessed by participants in the UK

Country	Tool/Technology	Event	Total number of participants	Number of Farmers	Number of Researchers	Number of Advisors	Other
UK	EID stick reader	NWS4	6	5		1	
	Farm management software	NWS4	6	5		1	
	Drone	TNWS4	6	5		1	
	Virtual Fence	TNWS4	6	5		1	

	DNA parentage	Industry meeting	5				5
	FecPak2	TNWS5	4		3	1	

NWS4 – National Workshop 4; TNWS4 Trans-national Workshop 4; TNWS5 – Trans-national Workshop 5

3. Results

3.1. Digifarms: Training sessions. Individual questionnaires

Table 11. Overall individual questionnaire results

<i>Please tick your answer</i>	Not at all	No	Yes	Yes a lot
1. Did you have the tool on your farm?		67.10%	32.90%	
2. Did you like it?	16.36%	1.52%	60.30%	21.82%
3. Was it easy to use?	12.17%	2.12%	70.11%	15.61%
4. Would you have the infrastructure needed to implement it?	25.20%	3.52%	65.31%	5.96%
5. Could you implement it on your farm easily?	24.15%	3.69%	64.77%	7.39%
6. Is it affordable to you?	32.69%	9.97%	50.69%	6.65%
7. Could you justify investing in it?	29.53%	8.19%	52.05%	10.23%
8. Do you think it would take long to pay it back?	40.00%	4.17%	41.94%	13.89%
9. Do you understand better after training?	4.63%	0.77%	79.43%	15.17%
10. Would you recommend to somebody else?	20.57%	0.26%	2.34%	67.71%
11. Do you think you need more training/guides/YouTube video to use it more often?	50.90%	0.52%	45.99%	2.58%

Table 11 shows the results of individual questionnaires regardless the country and tool demonstrated on innovative farms. The overall results highlight that most of farmers (67%) do not the demonstrated technologies have on their farms although they really liked them (82%) and even though they are easy to be used (86%). A large proportion of farmers (65%) would have the infrastructure to easily implement the technologies on their farm although only 57% of them believe that is affordable and could justify investing in them (62%), probably because it could take a long time to pay them back (56%).

A great proportion of people (95%) understood better the use of the technologies presented after the training and would recommend them to somebody else (70%), thus potentially highlighting the usefulness of such events. However, only 46% of people would need extra training and this is probably because of the information acquired on that day was satisfactory.

The following graphs (Figures 2-12) show the answers divided by country and technology demonstrated during training sessions on Digifarms. The number of technologies tested varied according to the country although some of them were common, in particular those associated to the EID readers. These tools have become widespread since electronic identification of animals became mandatory in Europe, and most farmers across the countries had these tools (Question 1. Do you have this tool?). Regarding the appreciation of the technologies (Question 2. Did you like it?) we can observe that almost all the technologies were liked across the partners and were evaluated as easy to use (Question 3. Was it easy to use?) apart from some of them, as indicated in blue and orange lines on the figures. The distribution of participants who had the infrastructure to implement the technologies demonstrated was varied (Question 4. Would you have the infrastructure needed to implement it?) and this is probably related to the dimensions and costs of the devices that would also affect the easiness of implementing them on farm (Question 5. Could you implement it on your farm easily?) and their affordability (Question 6. Is it affordable to you?). In each country, there were farmers who said they could justify investing in technologies (Question 7. Could you justify investing in it?) and who thought that it would not take much time to pay it back (Question 8. Do you think it would take long to pay it back?). However, there were a great variability across countries, as it is device dependant. Much agreement was found for the question 9 (Do you understand better after training); all participants clearly appreciated the training sessions and would recommend them to other people (Questions 9 and 10). It was clear that most people enjoyed the sessions, probably partly because they were organized in research and demonstrations farms, where specialist researchers and technicians could transfer their experience to the participating farmers.

Figure 2. Digifarm sessions: Do you have the tool on your farm?

Figure 3. Digifarm sessions – Do you like the tool(s) you have on your farm?

Figure 4. Digifarm sessions – Was it easy to use the tool(s)?

Figure 5 – Digifarm sessions – Would you have the infrastructure needed to implement the tool (s)?

Figure 6. Digifarm sessions – Could you implement the tool (s) easily on your farm?

Figure 7. Digifarm sessions – Is the tool(s) affordable to you?

Figure 8. Digifarm sessions – Could you justify investing in the tool (s)?

Figure 9. Digifarm sessions – Do you think it would take long to pay the tool(s) back?

Figure 10. Digifarm sessions – Do you understand better after training?

Figure 11. Digifarm sessions – Would you recommend the tool(s) to somebody else?

Figure 12. Digifarm sessions – Do you think you need more training/guides/YouTube videos to use the tool(s) more often?

3.2. Digifarms: Training sessions. Before-After questionnaires

Table 12. Overall results of Before-After questionnaires

<i>Please tick your answer</i>	<i>Maybe</i>	<i>No</i>	<i>Yes</i>
<i>BEFORE - what do you think of this technology?</i>	19.34%	18.11%	62.55%
<i>BEFORE - would you put it on your farm?</i>	8.53%	25.60%	65.87%
<i>AFTER - what do you think of this technology?</i>	25.08%	24.44%	50.48%
<i>AFTER - would you put it on your farm?</i>	9.28%	28.12%	62.61%

Table 12 shows the overall evaluation of the technologies before and after they were demonstrated. Positive answers were collected before the training (62.55%) that decreased a bit along the sessions (50.48%), probably their awareness on both positive and negative aspects of the technologies seen has increased. Most of people would put the technologies tested on their farm both before and after the sessions (66% and 63% respectively).

The following figures (Figure 13 – 18) show the answers for each country and technology tested.

UK answers show an increase in positive feedback for both technologies seen; an increasing number of people which would put them on their farm was also recorded. In Italy the evaluation of the technologies remained quite stable, although some undecided people changed opinion and decided “not to put” them on farm after the sessions. It is possible that in that case, the trialled devices were considered adequate only for experimental purposes. Ireland and France showed stable trends for both questions. Estonia improved a bit the evaluation of technologies after the training although some undecided people changed to “not to put” on their farm after the sessions. In Israel a decline on appreciation of one technology was observed while the opinion on putting them on farm had an opposite trend for the remaining device.

Figure 13. UK answers – what do you think of the technologies and would you put them on your farms?

Figure 14. Italy answers - what do you think of the technologies and would you put them on your farms?

Figure 15 -Ireland answers - what do you think of the technologies and would you put them on your farms?

Figure 16 – France answers - what do you think of the technologies and would you put them on your farms?

Figure 17 – Estonia answers - what do you think of the technologies and would you put them on your farms?

Figure 18. Israel answers - what do you think of the technologies and would you put them on your farms?

3.3. Innovative farms: Demo Days sessions. Before-After questionnaires

3.3.1 Estonia Innovative farms results

Figure 18. Estonia’s results

Figures 18 -25 show the results from the questions asked during the Innovative Farms sessions, by country.

In Estonia, two technologies were presented during the innovative farm sessions (Figure 18). Most of the participants had those devices and believed that it was worth investing in them and implementing them on their farms. Results were quite similar before and after the sessions. The level of practicality was set as quite good (4).

3.3.2 France Innovative farms results

Figure 19. France’s results

In France, apart from one device, very few farmers had the presented technologies (Figure 19). Farmers' opinions regarding the worth of investing in those technologies and implementing them on their farms remained quite stable before and after the demonstration days. The level of practicality differed among technologies and changed after the session for some devices.

3.3.3 Hungary Innovative farms results

Figure 20. Hungary's results

Figure 20 shows that Hungarian farmers owned between 1 and 2 of the technologies presented, however, they said they would invest on them and put on their farms. Their opinion did not change much after the sessions. The level of practicality did not change much easier, set at around 4.

3.3.4 Ireland Innovative farms results

Figure 21. Ireland's results

In Ireland, only one or two technologies presented were already owned by the participants (Figure 21). Farmers' opinion on investing in those technologies and putting them on their farms were quite similar before and after the farm demonstration days. However, the perceived levels of practicality varied before and after the farm demonstration sessions.

3.3.5 Israel Innovative farms results

Figure 22. Israel's results

In Israel, quite a lot of participating farmers owned at least 2 of the three technologies presented (Figure 22). Most of them believed it was worth investing in them and would put on their farms. There was no major change in their opinion before and after the farm demonstration sessions. The level of practicality was set at around 4 and did not change before and after the demonstrations.

3.3.6 Italy Innovative farms results

Figure 23. Italy's results

Most of the Italian farmers did not have the technologies showed during the farm demonstration days (Figure 23) although they would invest in them and put on their farms. Their opinions did not differ much before and after the demonstration days. The level of practicality was around 3 and 4 for most of devices presented both before and after the sessions.

3.3.7 Norway Innovative farms results

Figure 24. Norway's results

Most of the Norwegian farmers did not have the technologies presented apart from one (EID stick reader), as seen in Figure 24. There was not much change in farmers' opinions before and after the sessions. The level of practicality was set at around 3 and 4 and did not change much before and after the sessions.

3.3.8 UK Innovative farms results

Figure 25. UK results.

Two or three of the technologies presented to farmers in the UK were quite commonly owned by participating farmers (Figure 25). Farmers said they would like investing and putting on their farms most of devices showed during the demonstration days. There was not much change before and after the farm demonstrations. The level of practicality was variable according to the technology and farmers’ opinion changed after the farm demonstrations.

3.4. ADOPT general results

A total of 45 different ADOPT sessions have been completed to date, covering 24 different tools and technologies.

3.4.1 Questions influencing peak adoption level

The most sensitive questions, associated with the peak adoption level outputs, are summarised in Figure 26A. The questions influential were those related to **the scale of the sheep/goat enterprise** and the **potential profit benefit during the years that the tool or technology were used** (questions 4 and 16 respectively). Out of the 45 completed ADOPT sessions to date, 19 sessions highlighted question 4, and 16 sessions highlighted question 16, as sensitive in terms of influencing the peak adoption level. The remaining sessions found questions 19 (n=9) and 17 (n = 1) also influential. (See Table 1 for question details).

3.4.2. Questions influencing time to peak adoption

The most sensitive questions, associated with the length of time to peak adoption, are summarised in Figure 26B. The majority were related to the proportion of farmers that would **need to develop substantial new skills and knowledge to use the tool or technology** (question 12). Out of the 45 completed ADOPT sessions to date, 33 sessions highlighted question 12 as sensitive in terms of influencing the time to peak adoption. The remaining sessions found questions 6 (n = 1), 7 (n=8), 8 (n = 2) and 10 (n = 1) also influential. These were **mainly associated with the learnability characteristics** of the tool or technology. For example, question 7 related to how easily the tool or technology could be trialled on a limited basis before a decision could be made to adopt. (See Table 1 for question details).

Figure 26. Most sensitive questions highlighted during each ADOPT session relating to predicted level of peak adoption (A) and time to reach near peak adoption level (B) (details of each question given in Table 2)

Figure 27. Overview of ADOPT session outputs across each country

3.4.3. ADOPT sessions overview

Figure 27 summarises all 45 ADOPT sessions, carried out to date, and the tool or technology considered. The **predicted adoption level**, or time to near peak adoption, ranged from 2 years (Norway – Virtual Fence) to 24 years (Ireland – EID stick reader), with **an overall average of 11 years** across all sessions. The **peak adoption level percentage** ranged from 1% (Estonia – Virtual Fence) to 98% (5 different tools or technologies across 7 different sessions – drone, GPS collars, camera, milk meters & farm management software), with **an overall average of 60%**. Hungary and Norway had the highest proportion of sessions with peak adoption levels over 90% (3 out of 4 and 7 out of 10 respectively). However, this may be influenced by the types of tools and technologies assessed by each of these countries. For example, in Norway, some of the technologies assessed are already familiar to, or commonly used by, farmers such as the virtual fence and GPS collars.

3.4.4. Technologies assessed across more than one country

There were six tools or technologies assessed by ADOPT sessions across more than three countries: EID stick reader; virtual fence collar; GPS collars, RFID database; drone and camera (Figure 28). In general, the EID stick seemed popular, with peak adoption levels across the four countries all over 70% (range of 72% to 97%). The predicted number of years to peak adoption was similar across Estonia, Hungary and the UK (9-13 years), with Ireland predicting longer with 24 years. The GPS collars also had a very high predicted peak adoption level (74% to 98%). The time to near peak adoption ranged from 3 years (Norway) to 14 years (Israel). It should be noted that two of these sessions were held in Norway where the use of this technology is already popular when animals are on the extensive summer grazings.

More variation was observed for the virtual fence collars. Both Estonia and the UK had a very low peak adoption level (1% and 2% respectively). However, the two sessions carried out in Norway were higher at 61% and 93%. The predicted number of years to peak adoption was 23 and 11 in Estonia and the UK respectively. The two Norwegian sessions were 2 years and 11 years. The differences between these two Norwegian sessions could be due to differences in the level of existing skills (as highlighted by question 12 – Table 1) in the farmer groups providing feedback. The groups that had a short time to near peak adoption suggested that almost none of the population would need to develop new skills and knowledge to use the innovation, whereas the second group suggested about half of the population would.

Results for the drone and camera were variable across the different countries, with Norway having the highest predicted peak adoption levels across both technologies (98% for both). The lowest for the drone and camera were Estonia (34%) and Italy (12%) respectively. The length of time to near peak adoption, for both technologies, ranged from years (Hungary – camera) to 17 years (UK – drone). The RFID database had high predicted peak adoption levels in both Hungary and Norway (96% in both), but slightly lower in Ireland (61%). Similarly, the number of years to peak adoption were low in Hungary and Norway (5 and 7 years respectively) but slightly longer in Ireland (15 years).

Figure 28. Overview of ADOPT sessions carried out on the same tool/technology across different countries.

3.4.5. Summary of each tool and technology assessed to date

An overall average peak adoption level and time to near peak adoption, for the 24 tools or technologies assessed so far by participants during the ADOPT sessions are given in Table 13. The overall average, across the 45 sessions, was a 60% peak adoption level and 11 years to near peak adoption. Fourteen tools or technologies have only been assessed once, but for the remaining 10 that have been the subject of more than one ADOPT session, the average peak level of adoption ranged from 39.25% (virtual fence) to 92% (GPS collars). The predicted length of time to near peak adoption ranged from 5.5 years (EID parlour reader) to 15 years (milkimeters).

Table 1 Details of the ADOPT sessions carried out, per tool or technology.

Tool / Technology	Count of ADOPT sessions carried out to date	Average of Adoption level - Time to near peak adoption (years)	Average of Peak adoption level (%)
Autodrafter	2	13.0	44.00%
Automatic feeder	1	5.0	17.00%
Automatic post-milking spray	1	4.0	38.00%
Camera	4	7.8	70.75%
Connected Fence	1	12.0	16.00%
Conveyor	1	11.0	3.00%
DNA parentage	1	18.0	16.00%
Drone	4	13.3	57.50%
EID (bolus) parlour reader	2	5.5	59.00%
EID stick reader	4	14.3	84.75%
EID weigh crate	1	16.0	24.00%
Farm management software	1	14.0	98.00%
FecPak2	1	8.0	58.00%
Fire detection system	1	11.0	32.00%
GPS	4	7.5	92.00%
Milk feeder	1	15.0	7.00%
Milk tank weighing	1	8.0	76.00%
Milkmeters	2	15.0	63.50%
Pregnancy scanning	1	3.0	97.00%
RFID database	3	9.0	84.33%
Virtual Fence	4	11.8	39.25%
Walk over weigher	2	11.5	47.00%
Water meter	1	22.0	72.00%
Water trough	1	13.0	81.00%
All combined	45	11.0	60.00%

4. Conclusions

Training sessions on Digifarms and demonstration days on innovative farms have been proved to be good instruments to **foster practical knowledge** among stakeholders. It has been a valuable transfer of information and skills between both the researchers, who had the opportunity to get farmers' opinions, and farmers, who had a hands-on opportunity to try out various technologies and discuss with their peers the pros and cons without barriers due to educational level. For some countries and some technologies, these sessions changed favourably farmers' opinions regarding their potential uptake of technologies.

Feedback from the different ADOPT sessions carried out so far has also provided valuable information in terms of the predicted future uptake and acceptance of the different tools and technologies

highlighted by the Sm@RT project as possible solutions to issues raised previously in the project (D2.1). The answers given by participants also provide information relating to the possible barriers that may be influential in terms of improving uptake of certain tools and technologies.

Overall, the most sensitive questions associated with the predicted level of peak adoption were related to the **scale of the sheep/goat enterprise and the potential profit benefit during the years** that the tool or technology were used. The predicted length of time to reach the near peak adoption level was influenced heavily by the answers provided relating to what proportion of the populations would **need to develop substantial new skills and knowledge to use the tool or technology** that was being assessed. The **ability to trial the tools or technologies before a decision was made** to adopt them into the farming system was also highlighted as an important factor to consider.

The main themes highlighted by these outputs are themes that the overall Sm@RT project is working towards. By improving **training** and providing farmers the **opportunities to try and test** the different tools and technologies on farm during the digifarms and innovative farms' sessions, the project has **improved potential uptake** by the sector across Europe. This further reinforces the value of these events to help farmers make more informed decisions when considering which tools and technologies would be most beneficial to their farming system.

